

GETTY IMAGES: COPYRIGHT HAWK OR CORPORATE APPROPRIATOR?

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Abstract

This working paper explores the dual pull, often felt at both organisational and individual levels, towards simultaneously asserting one's own intellectual property and appropriating other people's. It does so with specific reference to Getty Images, the largest commercial archive in the world. The paper begins by scrutinizing how Getty Images amassed and safeguards its vast image repository, highlighting three elements that have underpinned its rapid growth: takeovers, litigation, and platformisation. The paper's focus then shifts to the role of appropriation in the company's historical and current activities, and in particular to how the company differs from public archives in how it approaches content with ambiguous copyright. The paper concludes by reflecting on the current legal dispute between Getty Images and Stability AI, and highlighting the contradictory stance held by Getty Images towards the emergence of generative AI.

Introduction

A few years ago I attended a discussion at the Institute of Contemporary Arts (ICA) in London on the subject of copyright for artists. The chairperson began the event with a question: 'Who is here because you want to protect the copyright of your own works?'. About half of audience put

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² Bartolomeo Meletti is Creative Director for CREATE, the Centre for Regulation of the Creative Economy at the University of Glasgow.

their hands up. Then he asked: 'Who is here because you want to make use of somebody else's work?'. Once again, about half of the audience put their hands up.

Anyone who knows even a bit about copyright is probably aware of the fundamental tension between protecting one's own intellectual property and utilising other people's IP. Often in popular discourse, rights holders and users are pitched against each other as distinct and opposed entities. But often these dual tendencies – to protect IP and to appropriate it – can be embodied within the same entity, the same organization, and even the same person. In fact, I would bet that most people who were at the ICA event were at least a little bit curious about both protecting their own property and reusing others'. Perhaps, if we had all been completely honest, we would have put our hands up twice.

In this working paper, I want to explore this dual pull, and look at how it plays out in the activities of one company in particular: Getty Images. First, I'll look at how the company has built up its store of intellectual property and how it has defended it. I'm then going to flip my attention to look at how appropriation also plays a role in Getty's past and present activities. I'll finish by touching on how this apparent contradiction applies to the unresolved question of how copyright relates to AI; specifically I'll consider how it relates to the current high-profile court case between Getty Images and Stability AI, which is likely to become a landmark case regarding the future legality of using unlicensed training data sets for generative AI systems.

Building and protecting IP

Perhaps the first question to address is: why Getty Images? What makes this particular company worthy of attention? One answer is that it is, in its own words, 'the largest commercial archive in the world' and consequently holds a dominant position within the contemporary image economy. Without realising it, we all see numerous images licensed by Getty Images every day – for example, on websites, news media, blogs, in adverts, and across social media.

As copyright plays such a major role in the circulation of images, and as images in turn comprise such an important focus for copyright law, it is of more than academic interest how Getty Images engages with copyright. A second answer to the question is that Getty Images is also a typical intermediary, and its approach to copyright could be seen as symptomatic of the wider creative industries' dual approach to copyright (as protector and user) as well as its reliance on these two approaches.

The final explanation for my interest in Getty Images is longer and more personal. For now, I'll just summarise it briefly. My background, going back about 10-15 years is as a video essayist and film-

maker; I make videos and films out of pre-existing videos and films. A few years ago, I became interested in working with historical archive footage (in particular, twentieth century newsreel footage) rather than just using clips from movies. But I could barely find any good quality source material online. There is a lot of visually low-quality content on YouTube, which is not professionally usable; there is some higher-quality archive footage on the Internet Archive. However, most of the good stuff exists behind archives' paywalls and is only accessible at a cost that is prohibitively high for independent creators like me. My current research project on Getty Images came out of this frustration of not being able to access the kind of footage I wanted to access as a film-maker. My first step in this project was a short film, *A History of the World According to Getty Images* (2022), made out of archive footage sourced from Getty Images' online catalogue, which involved creative reuse and is also about the difficulty accessing historic film and video. Specifically, the film came out of a frustration that so many clips that are legally in the public domain (i.e. out of copyright) are behind pay walls, and that's what the rest of the film ended up being about: the film addresses the specific legal and ethical issue of the lack of public access to public domain images. The film is freely available online, and comes with a twist that many people who are supportive of the public domain have very much enjoyed, so please do watch it.³

I'm still very much interested in the public domain as a theme, but in the year or so since the film came out, I've also become more widely interested in how the image economy functions and how Getty Images' recent practices fit within the paradigm of what has variously been called rentier capitalism, platform capitalism, techno-feudalism, cloud capitalism, and so on. Every theorist of this phenomenon is giving it a different name right now, but whatever you call it, it's a thing, and Getty, it turns out, is extremely good at it. Through talking about the film at various film festivals and conferences, I've started to realise that Getty Images is a quintessential platform capitalist.

But let's begin at the beginning. Getty Images is quite a young company. It was established in 1995 by Mark Getty, son of John Paul Getty Jr., and is only a few years older than Google. Not entirely coincidentally, 1995 is also a symbolically significant year because that was when the National Science Foundation privatized the last part of the public internet in the USA, and the internet effectively became private. What's particularly interesting to me is that unlike Google or Facebook, which created a completely new kind of product, Getty entered what was already a mature market for stock images. Yet in less than a decade, it was already the hegemonic company within this market. How did Getty Images reach market dominance so fast? I wish to

³ <https://www.ahistoryoftheworldaccordingtogettyimages.com>

focus on three key processes at play. All of them, to give away the punchline of this paper, are straight out of the techno-feudalist rulebook.

The first process is takeovers. If you're a commercial archive and you don't have a lot of content, buy a company that does. Especially in its first ten years, Getty Images, buoyed by the Getty dynasty's capital, spent many hundreds of millions of dollars buying out competing image archives including Tony Stone Images, World View, OnlineUSA, Allsport, art.com, iStockPhoto, Archive Photos of New York, the Hulton Press Archive, MediaVast, and JupiterImages. A number of these archives were themselves the results of prior mergers – for example, Archive Photos of New York was itself the result of a 1990 merger between two US photo agencies: Pictorial Parade (established in 1935) and Frederick Lewis Stock Photos (established in 1938). So historically Getty can be seen as a meta-archive, an archive of archives.

The second process, which underpins the first, is litigation. Once you've got lots of intellectual property, what do you do to protect it? You litigate, or at least you threaten litigation. You make it known that the content is yours, and you'll do whatever you need to protect it. From the late 2000s onwards, evidence from various news reports suggests that Getty adopted a highly aggressive approach towards perceived copyright infringers, no matter how small. For example, a 2008 article in *The Guardian* details how Getty sent a £6,000 bill to a local church in Lincolnshire for a number of images used on its website. The communications director of the church's diocese commented to the newspaper, 'The issue is not that photographs are free on the net for anyone to use, but that enforcement has to be done properly. Getty was basically bullying... not playing ball or following the normal litigation or dispute resolution procedures...'. By the early 2010s, Getty's legal threats had become so common that various websites and webpages, not to mention multiple threads on bulletin boards, had sprung up offering advice on how to respond to an aggressive demand for payment by the company. Notable among these is [extortionletterinfo.com](https://www.extortionletterinfo.com/) (ELI),⁴ 'the definitive informational website in the U.S. to combat and defend against Getty Images' (& other stock photo) extortionistic letter practices'. ELI's website is still live, though traffic to it peaked in 2014, which suggests that Getty may have since stepped back from 'bullying' accidental infringers. Perhaps the widespread media attention around Getty's litigious tendencies did the company's work for it. On the one hand, the media reports of the period helped give the company a certain notoriety, which – from the evidence of the responses that I typically get when I tell people about my research – continues to the present. At

⁴ <https://www.extortionletterinfo.com/>

the same time the potential negative publicity stemming from this media attention was counterbalanced, and perhaps even outweighed, by a clear message: don't mess with Getty.

It is of course very difficult to track small cease and desist claims, as most of the time they are settled out of court and so never become publicly-known. So I cannot track how many small claims Getty currently makes against perceived infringers. It is much easier, though, to track large claims involving the company. Two recent disputes in particular stand out. The first of these was with Google. On 15th February 2018, the 'View image' button – a deep link that connected directly to source image files on websites' servers – disappeared from Google image search. In an instant, it was like it had never existed. An article from the same day in *Android Authority* sought to reassure readers that their memory was not faulty: the view image button did indeed once exist, but no longer.⁵ Though no explanation for this change was given at the time, it occurred in response to a threatened \$6 billion lawsuit by Getty Images against Google. Getty claim that the 'View image' button encouraged wide-scale copyright infringement never made it to court: Google settled with Getty Images for an undisclosed sum and took the button away. The only options that you now have when you use Google image search are 'Visit website' and 'share' (meaning share the link, of course, not share the image). Getty Images is so powerful, it can make Google change its mind.

The second case that I want to highlight is Getty's current court action against UK-based generative AI startup Stability AI. In January 2023, Getty Images launched a claim against Stability for copyright violation linked to its generative image system Stable Diffusion. Many claims against generative AI companies have followed since, including a lawsuit filed a few weeks ago by *The New York Times* against OpenAI and Microsoft. However, lest we forget, it was Getty Images who launched the first legal case against a generative AI company. Here, once again, Getty has shown itself to be a real innovator in the use of litigation to defend its interests.

Platformisation: a new tool for restricting access to culture

I've so far identified two factors that help explain how Getty became so big so fast: takeovers and threatened litigation. The third factor that I highlight is so significant it could form a whole paper in itself. It is that Getty has the best platform in the business. To appropriate the phrase of another tech giant, it *just works*. The online catalogue is intuitive, the search and filter functions are powerful and accurate, and the shopping basket works even more seamlessly than Amazon's.

⁵ C. Scott Brown, 'Google removes View Image button in image search results', *Android Authority*, 15th February 2018. <https://www.androidauthority.com/google-removes-view-image-button-image-search-results-838307/>. Accessed 18th January, 2024.

Compare this to many (especially public) archives, where to get clips you still have to hire a researcher by the hour just to find out what's actually in the archive in the first place, and Getty's appeal becomes clear. Its popularity becomes even more on consideration of who its main client base is. Getty has three main markets. The first is the media – TV, print, and online publishing, including news stations and newspapers. The second is creative professionals in the advertising and graphic design sectors. The third is corporate – corporate communications, in-house design, conferences, etc. All three of these client segments value speed and ease of access over cost. They are generally willing to pay whatever is needed to get the image they want right now, and Getty's platform makes that possible. You could probably spend half million dollars on it within an hour. As a result, ease of use, combined with the knowledge that it has more images than anyone else, makes Getty Images the default supplier to the image industry. As it is a default supplier across the creative industries, that of course also gives it huge power over the creatives whom the company employs to supply those images. If you are a photographer and you want to get your images onto the BBC or into *The New York Times*, the best path to do it is through Getty Images. The result of this is that Getty have what Rebecca Giblin and Corrie Doctorow refer to in their superbly researched book *Chokepoint Capitalism* as a 'chokepoint': a strong element of monopoly power over its clients combined with a strong element of monopsony power over its suppliers, allowing the company to charge premium prices to consumers whilst squeezing suppliers. In short, Getty is the Uber of the image industry, but far, far more profitable.

Over recent years intellectual property has become intimately tied up with ownership and control of platforms. If you think of IP as a physical property – a building – then a platform is the land on which the building stands. For anyone who's interested in access to culture, both the property and the land on which it stands are equally important: not having access to the land around a property is just as great a barrier to access as being locked out of the property itself. *A History Of The World According To Getty Images* was about one specific example of the symbiotic relationship between platforms and property: the way in which commercial archives use paywalls to restrict access to historical footage regardless of whether they have intellectual property rights over it or not (though it should be noted that this is not a practice that is restricted to commercial archives: public archives, increasingly pressured to operate as businesses, also often do this).

Streaming platforms provide another example of how platformisation can prevent access to culture just as effectively as copyright. The way in which copyright functions in relation to streaming platforms often leads to restrictions on access to films far in excess of what the law itself intends, because if no national distributor is willing to license a particular film, then the film

cannot be legally distributed in that particular country. So rather than simply ensuring that the rights holders of a film are paid for their work, copyright carries the significant externality of ensuring that many films cannot be seen at all in many countries. Platformisation complements copyright in limiting access to films. Though one might have expected that the platformisation of digital film distribution would have led to more widespread availability of films, it is now becoming clear that this has not been the case. Since the demise of DVD, users have become dependent on a small number of platforms for their domestic viewing. And most platforms are only interested in distributing the most mainstream content. If no major platform is interested in licensing a classic film such as *2001: A Space Odyssey* (as was the case until last year, when HBO Max picked it up), then the film remains out of legal circulation. Of course, HBO is also free to drop the film at any point in the future for any reason, and in effect withdraw it from circulation. And even if a platform does have a particular film in its collection, the more niche it is, the less likely it is to appear in users' recommendations: the streamer's algorithm effectively disappears the film.

A less overt example of the combined effect of copyright and platform power on access to culture can be seen in the recent legal wrangling around the planned takeover by Microsoft of video game giant Activision Blizzard. At one point both the Federal Trade Commission (FTC) and the UK's Competition and Markets Authority (CMA) seemed poised to block the takeover. In a final PR push, Microsoft made a guarantee to Sony and Nintendo that the *Call of Duty* franchise would remain available on Switch and PlayStation consoles for at least fifteen years outside the European Union.⁶ This seemingly minor concession worked: it was sufficient to persuade both the CMA and a Federal appeals judge (though not the FTC), and the takeover is now going ahead. To clarify what just happened: the deciding question in this \$69 billion takeover seems to have been not the risk of massive centralisation of economic power in the hands of one of the Big Five tech companies, but the risk of Microsoft withholding access to one of its games from competing platforms. As soon as Microsoft promised to open a small doorway into its walled garden, opposition abated. I have an intuition about what will happen once the fifteen-year guarantee lapses, though...

The above three examples suggest, at least to me, that the greatest creeping threat to the public's access to culture currently comes from platforms. For the moment at least, copyright seems quite stable (with one exception, AI, which I shall come back to in a moment). There does not seem to be any clear opportunity at the moment to pedal back on recent decades' drift

⁶ Karen Weise, Kellen Browning and David McCabe, 'How Microsoft Turned the Tide in Its Regulatory Fight Over Activision' *The New York Times*, 13th October 2023.

towards what Patricia Aufederheide and Peter Jaszi refer to as ‘long and strong’ copyright⁷ (though of course there remains much work to be done around clarifying copyright exceptions, an area in which CREATE continues to do world-leading research).⁸ Nor, conversely, is anyone seriously talking about extending the length copyright even further than death plus 70 years. Even Disney seems not to be pushing its luck; on 1st January 2024, after two previous near misses, *Steamboat Willy* quietly entered the public domain. Overall, for better or worse, copyright feels like it is currently in legal equilibrium. Most platforms, by contrast, are still in extreme flux, searching for the best combination of advertising and subscription to maximise their profits, while all the time adapting to on-going technological and legislative changes. What the digital landscape will look like in a decade is anyone’s guess, but it is clear that the parameters by which we engage with culture will in future be set by platforms as much as by copyright law. And I only need mention Elon Musk’s takeover of Twitter to highlight the particular dangers of private control over platforms that act as *de facto* public services. For this reason, my personal feeling is what we most urgently need now is not copyright reform, but more, bigger, and better publicly owned and publicly controlled platforms. How to bring these about, though, is a whole other question.

The Appropriative Cycle

The uncle of a friend of mine once co-managed a winery during Communist days. At one point soon after 1989 his co-manager drove up in a van with some associates carrying baseball bats, walked into his office and said, ‘This factory is mine now’. That was all it took, at that moment in history, to get control of a multi-million Euro business. To appropriate is to say ‘This is mine’ and know you have the power to enforce that statement. To appropriate is also to know that though there may be people who may object to your appropriation, there is nothing they can do about it. Appropriation is an expression of power. Of course, appropriation of cultural works is usually a lot less overt than the violent appropriation of physical property, but it is also typically predicated on an imbalance of power.

The story so far is that Getty Images owns a lot of intellectual property and is known for aggressively defending it. But the irony underlining this fact is that Getty also appropriates. I

⁷ Patricia Aufederheide and Peter Jaszi (2011). *Reclaiming Fair Use: How to Put Balance Back in Copyright*. University of Chicago Press, p. 6.

⁸ For a recent and directly relevant example of CREATE’s work on clarifying copyright exceptions, see Meletti, B., & van Gompel, S. (2022). *Code of Best Practices on Creative Reuse for Documentary Filmmakers*. Zenodo.

want now to look at a couple of images that exists in Getty Images' catalogue but have in various ways been appropriated. Both examples involve clips that I used in my film.

Figure 1 'Villagers waving at the 24/7th mechanised infantry of the Ninth Infantry division moving into Cambodia'. Getty Images/Christopher Jensen.

This clip of American soldiers driving past Vietnamese villagers was shot by Christopher Jensen, a military photographer in the US Army. Several years ago, Jensen licensed this and many other clips to Getty Images: he is credited on Getty's website as both creator and owner. There are at least three layers of appropriation here. The first is colonial appropriation: the occupation of land by an invading power. This may not seem directly relevant to copyright, but control over space facilitates control over images; colonialism is the reason these images were originally shot, and subsequently monetized, by an American. Secondly, there is appropriation of physical property. Jensen was working for the army, but somehow he got to keep his hands on much of what he filmed, even after he returned from Vietnam; the reels stayed in his possession, which was also a necessary condition for him to be able to monetise them. Finally, there's appropriation of the public domain. As American government footage, this footage entered the public domain the moment it was filmed. There was never any copyright related it, but of course, its only

existence was in a film can in Christopher Jensen's possession, so regardless of what the law says, it was he who had control over it.

Several years ago, Jensen shared much of his footage on his personal YouTube account, so clearly was trying to do the right thing. Unfortunately, many of the videos that he posted have subsequently been taken down by YouTube as inappropriate content because they include graphic images of dead bodies (because, you know, this is war footage...). This is an important point also to highlight, though slightly off topic. Several times over the last year when I've been showing my film, people have said, 'I don't understand what the problem is because everything's freely available on YouTube nowadays'. My response is that YouTube is itself a part of the problem, not a solution to it. Once again, access to images becomes subject to corporate power: something that's up today could be taken down at any moment due to copyright trolling, or because the terms and conditions change, or for many other reasons. Most likely, sometime quite soon, Jensen will die, his account will be deactivated, and for all his goodwill, these images will revert to being available only through Getty's website. Unless measures are actively taken to archive and protect public domain images, sooner or later they will almost certainly be lost to the public.

Figure 2 'Chernobyl, aerial shot of damaged nuclear power plant, Pripjat, Ukraine, USSR'. Getty Images/Film Images Sarl.

The second clip that I want to discuss involves an even more complex appropriation. At least Jensen's footage was clearly in the public domain. This clip of Chernobyl, just after the accident in April 1986, has a much messier provenance and legal status. When researching an image's provenance, a researcher can go in two directions. They can start with what was filmed and investigate evidence within the image itself, or they can start with where they found the image and work backwards from its metadata. Both approaches are complementary in identifying a clip's provenance and copyright status. So how to identify the copyright status of this clip?

Evidence from the image itself suggests it was filmed in the weeks after the accident; about six weeks after the accident, the Soviets started to erect a temporary casing over the reactor core, which would have been visible had the shot been filmed later. It was probably filmed by the Soviet military, as access to helicopters by civilians was highly restricted, though at least one civilian documentarist – Volodymyr Shevchenko – did manage to film the site from a military helicopter. Given the radioactivity they must have been exposed to at this moment, the cameraperson is probably dead. If they were civilian, perhaps they had personal copyright over it and now it has passed to the family, but it is more likely that a state organisation such as Gosfilm had it. If they were military, presumably the Soviet army had copyright. But neither the Soviet army nor any Soviet institutions exist anymore, as the Soviet Union itself no longer exists. There might be a Russian lawyer somewhere who could find a path through this labyrinth of possibilities, but good luck in accessing one at this point in history. Alternatively, if one starts with the video file rather than the image itself, the path is even more blocked.

AERIAL Shot of damaged nuclear plant, deserted city pripyat AUDIO / Pripjat, Chernobyl, Ussr, Ukraine

AERIAL Shot of damaged nuclear plant, deserted city pripyat AUDIO / Pripjat, Chernobyl, Ussr, Ukraine

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SAVE TO CART

DETAILS

Credit: [Film Images Sarl - Footage](#)
 Editorial #: 137001482
 Collection: Archive Films: Editorial
 Date created: January 01, 1986
 License type: Rights-ready
 Release info: Not released. [More information](#)
 Clip length: 00:00:34:13
 Location: Pripjat, Chernobyl, Unspecified, Ukraine
 Mastered to: QuickTime 8-bit Photo-JPEG SD 720x576 25p
 Originally shot on: 35mm B/W Neg 576 25i
 Source: Archive Films Editorial
 Object name: 137001482

Figure 3 <https://www.gettyimages.no/detail/video/shot-of-damaged-nuclear-plant-deserted-city-pripyat-audio-news-footage/137001482>

Looking at the above catalogue entry on Getty's website, the metadata states when the footage was filmed (though the date fields for historic images on Getty's website are quite unreliable – here, for example, the 'date created' is almost four months before the disaster). The metadata also states that the footage was shot on 35mm black-and-white negative, which is clearly not true. It states the location where it was filmed, which in this case is obvious. And it also provides a credit; bizarrely, however, the credit field identifies neither who filmed it (not the director, the cameraperson, the production company, or the media agency behind it), nor who currently has copyright over it. Rather, it identifies 'Film Images Sarl', which is the archive that licensed the image to Getty. I contacted this archive while making my film, and they had no idea where the clip came from – and so, presumably, no legal title to the clip either.

In short, this clip has changed hands so many times since it was filmed that almost all its original metadata, of which there was probably not much anyway, has disappeared. So currently, this is an orphan clip. In my film, I focused specifically on how Getty Images appropriates public domain images. It seems, at least from the evidence of this clip, that the company is also not averse to appropriating orphan clips. This leads to me to the most important question of my talk.

How many of its assets does Getty Images own?

Getty Images has an archive of over 50 million 'assets' (to use their term). But owning a photographic print or a roll of film does not in itself entail intellectual property rights. Nor does digitising a clip and putting a watermark on it. Getty's editorial collection of historical images exemplifies what Claudy Op den Kamp refers to as the 'dichotomy between material and intellectual property'.⁹ So how much of its collection does Getty Images actually have clearly documented copyright over?

When I was making my film, I browsed all of the first 50 years of editorial video on Getty Images' online catalogue, starting in the 1890s and moving forward a page at a time until the 1950s, at which point the amount of digitised video snowballed and my search necessarily became far more selective. What is available online does not constitute the entirety of the images physically owned by Getty, but my guess is that it forms a large proportion of it. And from what I saw, I suspect that *most of the clips I browsed are orphans*. Thousands, perhaps tens of thousands, and possibly even hundreds of thousands of clips that are physically owned by Getty are not legally its intellectual property.

So how can it be that Getty is able to sell thousands of orphan clips? The answer is that it's all about risk. As any user of archival media knows, public archives tend to be quite conservative when it comes to intellectual property. If they were to make an orphan clip publicly available, it would open the possibility that the rights holder could appear and sue them for a sum of money that they couldn't afford. So usually, public archives only release media if they're sure that it's legal to do so. This means that most of the time a user can only access a clip if it's their copyright or if they can prove they have permission to use it. As a result, most orphan clips in most public archives are effectively inaccessible. The EU's Copyright in the Digital Single Market (CDSM) Directive could potentially change the balance of risk for public archives, and vastly improve the accessibility of their collections. The Directive allows archives to do a simple web search of images in their collection to check if they are currently being monetized by their rights holder. If

⁹ Claudy Op den Kamp (2017). *The Greatest Films Never Seen: The Film Archive and the Copyright Smokescreen*. Amsterdam University Press, p. 26.

there is no evidence that they are, archives can declare these images to be 'out of commerce' and release them publicly as if they were in the public domain. However, so far, only the Bundesarchiv in Germany has made significant use of the Directive: Adelheid Heftberger, Head of Film Access at the Bundesarchiv estimates that about 80% of images to have been released under the Directive by autumn 2023 came from their collection. It seems that most other archives are still nervous about the legal implications of releasing out-of-commerce clips (most of which would probably also be classified as orphan clips) into the public realm. If a public archive is fundamentally risk averse, one could argue that it doesn't matter what any EU Directive or subsequent national law allows it to do. If the archive does not have a strong culture of public access, it will always find ambiguities in the law that push it towards caution.

For Getty Images, however, the balance of risk is completely different. Let's think about the Chernobyl clip. What is the likelihood of Getty being able to make money from it? Probably very high: this is an iconic historical image. What is the risk of Getty being sued by the copyright holder? Probably very low. There's no metadata that identifies the rights holder; there's no clear evidence of when, how, or by whom the image was filmed; it was filmed in the Soviet Union, a political territory that no longer exists; and whoever filmed the image is probably by now dead, even if they didn't die of radiation poisoning very soon after the filming. The likelihood of someone suing Getty Images for releasing this clip is infinitesimal. And even in the highly unlikely event that a rights holder comes forward with a claim, the cost to settle is going to be far less than the revenue that Getty Images gains from licensing many thousands of orphan clips, and just a drop in the ocean of its annual revenue. One might liken the structural motivators here to those faced by private water companies responsible for massive amounts of sewage discharge in the sea around the UK: they know they'll get caught and fined once in a while, but keeping on doing it and absorbing the fines is far more profitable than overhauling their entire infrastructure.

Getty Images can easily absorb the risk of releasing images with an ambiguous intellectual property status. And that, incidentally, is one of the things that makes them so attractive to clients: if you license a clip from Getty, you are indemnified for the use of that clip. If a rights holder comes after you, Getty will foot the bill. So, while public archives treat uncertainty over images' copyright status as a red light, Getty has no problem with ambiguous IP. In a way, orphan clips of iconic historic events could even be regarded as perfect assets: they're old and their copyright information is probably untraceable, so there's nobody to pay royalties or licensing fees to. Getty already has the infrastructure to distribute them, so it's money for nothing.

This reminds me of the old legal adage that possession is nine-tenths of the law. This may have been true for physical property in Hungary in 1989, but it is certainly not true for intellectual property now: IP is now almost always clearly documented and actively asserted by its owners. However, there are still many ways a company can secure control over images (i.e. appropriate them) without having intellectual property rights over them. One method, as already mentioned, is takeovers, in which a large and powerful company such as Getty Images absorbs the assets of smaller and less powerful companies. Takeovers are definable as industrial-scale, legal appropriation.

A more recent way in which Getty Images has secured control over images without holding their IP has involved managing other archives' collections. In the mid-2010s, once Getty had developed its own digital storage and distribution system, it did what Amazon Cloud Services famously did in the late 2000s: it started to rent out its technology and services to other companies. Getty Images currently manages numerous audiovisual archives including those of the BBC and the Japanese Broadcasting Corporation (NHK), as well as the internal collections of many private sector clients. From the perspective of an organisation such as the BBC, allowing Getty Images to manage its archive is an attractive proposition. Getty has the best platform into the industry; they also have the largest commercial client base in the industry, providing the BBC with access to new markets; and they take care of all the logistics of selling the images, which allows the BBC (whose budget has been progressively squeezed for many years) to save money by outsourcing labour. No matter that Getty probably retains an eye-wateringly high percentage of the profit each time it sells one of the BBC's images, the arrangement still probably benefits both parties. Even if the economic benefits to the BBC are not especially great, the longer that Getty Images manages the BBC's collection, the more deeply intertwined its technology becomes within the BBC's archive (now called the 'BBC Motion Gallery'), and the more likely its contract is to be renewed. And so it came to pass last year, when Getty's 'Global Representation Partnership' with BBC Studios was renewed for a further five years.¹⁰

The cost of this arrangement to the public and to the creative sector, however, is a public image archive that is managed according to the logic of a multinational corporation. Getty is now the BBC Motion Gallery's sole public interface, so almost all decisions about who gets access to its collection are made by Getty Images' staff on an economic basis. The possibility of artists initiating the kinds of collaborations with the BBC that they routinely do with more public-facing

¹⁰ Press release: 'Getty Images and BBC Studios Renew 5 Year Global Representation Partnership', <https://newsroom.gettyimages.com/en/getty-images/getty-images-and-bbc-studios-renew-5-year-global-representation-partnership>, 15th November 2022. Accessed 18th January, 2024.

archives such as that of the Eye Filmmuseum or The Netherlands Institute for Sound & Vision is virtually zero. If you want to create an artwork using content from the BBC, unless you have a lot of money or are called Adam Curtis, then good luck.

Perhaps the most opaque example of Getty using its market dominance to become the gatekeeper for another company's archive is its co-operative agreement with Chinese image distributor Visual Graphics China (VGC). Remember Corbis? For a time in the early 1990s, Corbis was one of Bill Gates's pet projects. Like Getty a few years later, Corbis quickly built up its collection by taking over various smaller companies, and built a giant archive under a mountain in Pennsylvania to house it. Inevitably, for a long time Corbis was itself on Getty Images' wish list. But for reasons unknown, Getty never managed to take it over. However, in 2016, Corbis was taken over by VGC. Within a few weeks, VGC and Getty had announced a collaborative agreement by which VGC got exclusive rights to Getty's content in China, and Getty got exclusive rights to VGC's content (including content formerly owned by Corbis) across the rest of the world. A very good deal indeed for Getty. It is with noting that I have found no further information about this agreement online. Neither Getty nor VGC have ever said much about it beyond acknowledging its existence, which is perhaps not surprising as it looks very much like an anti-competitive agreement. As such, one might imagine it would at the very least warrant attention by US and Chinese regulators. As far as I am aware, however, no such regulatory scrutiny has ever taken place. Getty's empire continues to expand virtually unchecked.

Getty Images v AI?

I want to conclude by connecting the above discussion of appropriation to the current legal dispute between Getty Images and Stability AI, and by briefly exploring the potential implications of the rise of generative AI for Getty's business model.

All the clips that I used and discussed in my film, including the two clips discussed above, are examples of 'editorial' content: journalistic images created by news organisations. They are images which have at least some degree of historical interest, and which are accordingly preserved in public or private archives. But here's the rub: though one might think of Getty Images as an archive, most of its income does not come from 'editorial' content. Instead, it comes from 'creative' images: the kind of generic, aestheticized images that we see in advertisements and corporate media. Pristine natural landscapes, time-lapse cityscapes, steaming cups of cappuccino, close-ups of microchips, happy commuters talking on their phones: visual wallpaper. A former Getty employee whom I interviewed while making my film suggested that about 80% of the company's profit comes from such 'creative' images. 'Creative'

images here in fact means uncreative images – images that look like, and are meant to look like, thousands of other images that you’ve seen before. Images, in other words, that look like they might have been created by a generative AI system.

If my interviewee’s estimate is anywhere near true, and I think it is, then this is a crunch moment for Getty. Generative AI is getting better by the month; it is already quite good at creating still images (though it still struggles with human subjects) and is also close to being able to generate high quality video. As a result, it poses an imminent and extreme threat to Getty’s core business. Unsurprisingly, the company has been quick to respond to this threat. In early 2023, Getty went in hard and fast against Stability AI, claiming that its AI image generator Stable Diffusion is a ‘brazen infringement of intellectual property on a staggering scale’.¹¹ A legal complaint was filed in late January in the UK and in early February in the USA, forming an attack on two fronts. Each complaint, in turn, includes multiple claims encompassing a range of grievances including copyright infringement, trademark infringement, and even – in a quite creative argument inspired by a mangled Getty Images watermark – misrepresentation resulting in reputational damage. The case centres on Getty’s claim that out of the 5.85 billion images that formed the training data for Stable Diffusion, 12 million came from its online catalogue. In the US case alone, Getty is seeking \$150,000 in statutory damages per image, which amounts to a total claim of \$1.8 trillion, excluding the additional damages that it is seeking for trademark infringement. An interim ruling by the UK’s High Court of Justice in December concluded that all of Getty’s main claims should be allowed to continue to trial.

Over the course of the last year, both sides’ arguments have gradually become more complex and multi-stranded, to the point where it is difficult to be sure where the main point of contention in each of the cases (which differ significantly from each other in their details) actually lies. If the interim ruling can be regarded as a snapshot of the unfolding UK case, then the crux currently seems not to be the issue that the world’s copyright experts and media have spent the last year debating (viz. whether training generative AI with copyright works requires permission from rights holders), but instead whether the UK is an appropriate country in which to pursue a claim against Stability, whose training data was gathered in Germany and whose cloud computing is based in the USA.

I do not intend now, at the tail end of an already long paper, to delve into the nuances of each of the two court cases in detail or to explore the larger question of whether generative AI could or should be regarded as fair use and/or fair dealing. All that I will say for the moment is that, despite

¹¹ Getty Images (US), Inc. v Stability AI, Inc. Case 1:23-cv-00135-UNA (2023).

a seemingly growing consensus among legal experts that generative AI is not inherently a copyright violation, this issue is very far from being settled. No matter who wins in each of Getty's cases and in the various other claims currently being made against generative AI companies, the loser(s) will almost certainly appeal. Given the cultural and economic significance of this issue, it is quite likely that the cases will ultimately be decided by the US and UK Supreme Courts. There is also the possibility that future AI laws may pre-empt these rulings or render them obsolete, for example by mandating some form of agreement with IP holders when datasets are used to train AI systems, or by extending fair dealing to include data mining for commercial purposes.

My main interest in this case is the way in which it underlines both Getty's hegemonic position within the image economy and its contradictory approach to copyright. First, the hegemony. Getty argues in both its UK and US claims that by downloading images from its online catalogue, Stability is directly competing with it. But it is important to note here that the images in question are not the high quality files that Getty implies they are. They are low resolution preview files with 'Getty Images' watermarks on them. The significance of the two below versions of Getty Images' watermark is worth lingering over for a moment.

Figure 4 Evidence submitted by the plaintiff in Getty Images v Stability AI (Case 1:23-cv-00135-UNA, District Court of Delaware)

Getty uses such examples of mangled watermarks as evidence of trademark violation. Katharina Trendecosta and Cory Doctorow, however, see it in another light – as evidence of the stranglehold that Getty has over the image economy. Nobody knows what input text led to the AI generated image on the right, nor what training data was used to generate it; the image on the left that Getty implies is a ‘source image’ is just an image from their collection that looks a bit like the generated image. Looking at it from the outside, we cannot know how the AI image was actually generated, and from what; we can just interpret. Trendecosta and Doctorow interpret a mangled Getty logo found on a similar image of a red carpet event, which I have not been able to find, but their argument is also applicable to the above image: ‘what’s really happening is that the image generator has “learned” that any image of a red carpet contains a Getty watermark, so it draws the watermark into images that seem “Getty-like.” In other words, Getty has such a lock on a certain kind of news photography that a statistical analysis of *all* newsworthy photos of celebrities will conclude that Getty is inseparable from that kind of photography.’¹² To extend this analysis to the football image used in Getty’s claim: as far as Stable Diffusion can see, all football pitches have a light patch in the shape of a Getty Images logo. It’s as if the Getty Images watermark has been stamped onto reality itself. I can’t think of a more apt metaphor for Getty Images’ hegemonic status within the image economy.

Second, to tie up my argument, I return to Getty’s contradictory approach to copyright. I started this paper by suggesting that most organisations and individuals in the cultural and creative industries have an interest both in protecting their own intellectual property and in using others’. I continued by demonstrating how Getty Images’ past and present actions exemplify this dual tendency. Of course, Getty’s desire to protect its own property and to appropriate others’ is not a contradiction at all. The company is just playing both sides of the field. When its bottom line is served by appropriating, it does so. When its bottom line is served by suing appropriators, it also does so. Why wouldn’t it?

Given Getty’s fluid movement between copyright hawkishness and appropriation, the latest twist in this story should come as no surprise. Last September, Getty announced that it was partnering with chip manufacturer NVIDIA to develop its own generative AI system. Getty has the largest privately-held image collection in the world, and is now teaming up with the biggest chip manufacturer in the world. The result, I don’t doubt, will be one of the best generative AI systems on the market, and may be the undoing of Stability (if the court case doesn’t undo it first).

¹² Katharine Trendacosta and Cory Doctorow, ‘AI Art Generators and the Online Image Market’, Electronic Frontier Foundation, 3rd April 2023. <https://www.eff.org/deeplinks/2023/04/ai-art-generators-and-online-image-market>. Accessed 7th December 2023.

But to return to my main question: how many of the assets in its collection does Getty Images actually own? Getty asserts that Stable Diffusion's training data includes 12 million images scraped from Getty's website, 'of which around 7.3 million are Copyright Works'.¹³ The phraseology is a bit vague, but the implication here is that Getty has the rights to 7.3 million images used to train Stable Diffusion. If this is so, then that means the remaining 4.7 million images are a mix of public domain and orphan images – an astonishingly high proportion of the training data.

The 7.3 million images are enough to give Getty a strong claim against Stability. But at the same time, the other 4.7 million images are surely enough to cause it some concern. Given the huge numbers involved, it is almost certain that rights holders of many of the orphan images are entities other than Getty Images and are still traceable. Equally ominous, for Getty's new venture, is the uncertainty about where AI law will go next. For example, the EU's forthcoming AI Act is likely to mandate 'publishing summaries of copyrighted data used for training'.¹⁴ Of course, it is still not clear what this means. It may not mean that all training data used in all generative AI systems will need to be copyright cleared: there is a possibility that generative AI systems may be able to use unlicensed training data in more than just non-commercial contexts. However, these words seem at least to point in the direction of some kind of transparency requirement around who owns the training data that AI image generators utilise. And if that proves to be the case, Getty's history of appropriation may yet come back to bite it.

And so, my final question: could it be that to succeed as a generative AI company, Getty Images may first need to lose its case against Stability?

¹³ Getty v Stability AI, Interim Ruling, High Court of Justice. Neutral Citation Number [2023] EWHC 3090 (Ch). December 1st 2023.

¹⁴ 'Artificial Intelligence Act: deal on comprehensive rules for trustworthy AI', European Parliament press release, 9th December 2024. <https://www.europarl.europa.eu/news/en/press-room/20231206IPR15699/artificial-intelligence-act-deal-on-comprehensive-rules-for-trustworthy-ai>. Accessed 7th December 2023.

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